

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND MASS SPORTS

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dzyodo - sports trainer

ABSTRACT The article is about the problems and solutions of Science Education in the field of physical education and sports, the study of professional educational benchmarks in physical education and sports activity of athletes, the close connection of sports federations with sports organizations in professional sports education, the formation of various sports education studies between problem situations and sports organizations of education.

KEY WORDS Education in sports activity, determination of the main tasks and goals of sports education, organization of sports educational programs, formation of the personnel market in the field of physical education and sports, education of athletes in various conditions.

As noted in the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 414 of November 2022, it is envisaged to obtain high results by training qualified personnel in the field of Physical Education and sports, adapting the educational process to international standards and digitizing the management system, further improving the pedagogical and scientific potential and radically improving the quality of research.

Formation of educational programs according to the program of a foreign higher educational institution with a high international rating, to ensure the academic exchange of students in cooperation with the world's leading higher educational institutions and to create broad conditions for Education, Accreditation of Bachelor's degrees and master's specialties, Organization of the educational process on the basis of a credit-modular system in order to constantly improve sports skills in students and to express their person on the basis of, graduates 'pre-graduation practice consists in organizing them by involving them in the process of training and training sessions of national teams abroad, as well as international competitions, based on the level of application of the students' knowledge, qualifications and skills in practice, providing talented graduates with certificates determining the qualification category of a sports referee and a second-class trainer.

The development of sports, the wide resolution of a healthy lifestyle in our society, the popularization of physical education and sports among the

population, especially among young people, have been marked as a sign of the important directions of the policy of our state since the first days of independence. Over the years, large-scale work has been carried out on this subject and tremendous results have been achieved. Over the past five years, 1 trillion 230 billion soums have been allocated for the development of Physical Culture and sports, as well as strengthening its material and technical base, and funds from the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan have also been spent.

Today, in order to further expand the mass involvement of children in sports, about 114, 8 thousand sports sections are operating in 1,700 children's sports facilities, which means 30 percent more than the 2020 indicators.

More than 3, 6 million residents are involved in sports sections and groups organized in gyms and sports clubs of all Umut education schools, children's and youth sports schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges in the Republic. More than 2, 1million of them are students and young people of secondary schools, professional colleges and academic lyceums.

Today, 10 thousand 75 teachers and coaches operate in sports facilities in the Republic, of which 4 thousand 667 are of Higher Education (43, 4percent, 5 thousand 599 are of secondary special education (56, 6 percent).Today our country is literally becoming a sports country. A healthy lifestyle among young people is widely decided and the popularity of sports is ensured. Athletes of Uzbekistan have won high victories in prestigious World competitions and show the sports potential of our country to the whole world. The results achieved by our athletes at the 2016 Olympic and Paralympic Games in Brazil and 2021 in Japan alone made our country known to the world sports community as a dynamically developing country. We are rightfully proud of this. But it is also necessary to say that in recognition of the achieved results, achievements, there are serious shortcomings and problems in improving the system of organization and management of the physical education and sports sphere, strengthening the material and technical base of the industry, broad involvement of youth in sports in the regions, creating sufficient conditions for them, training qualified personnel in For example, today, 67.6% of 9,698 secondary schools in the system of the Ministry of Public Education have gyms, while 32.4% do not have gyms. In total, 25 thousand 603 teachers of physical education work in schools. 17 thousand 735 of them (69.2 percent) have higher education, 7 thousand 868 (30.8 percent) have secondary special education.The number of teachers with secondary special education in the discipline of physical education is the majority in Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Samarkand,

Tashkent, Khorezm regions. The educational and methodological manual for teachers in the discipline of physical education was created in 2003, so far this manual has not been reprinted. There are 225 sports schools on the territory of the Republic, of which 53 are specialized sports schools for sports. In total, there are 318,693 people in these schools, of which 97,000 girls are regularly engaged in children's Sports, which means only 7.1% of total schoolchildren.

Someone is looking for happiness, and someone is the throne. Someone is looking for wealth, someone else is fame. Of course, this is a way of struggle for survival, which everyone wants: however, people want to find something in the course of their actions, and also face losses. Peace and quiet in fasting largely depends on the relationship of their parents. When a parent is a cow, this in itself serves as an example for children, young people who have grown up in a close family also live a sweet life like their father. The family is the basis of society. When the family is healthy, the nation is also healthy. The foundation is also laid in the family for the health, physical and mental perfection of the next generation. According to the custom of our people, each person must carry out three good deeds throughout his life, that is, the duty to raise 226 healthy and harmonious children, build a shelter for his family and plant seedlings with good intentions is absorbed in our blood. Every parent dreams that his child will grow up in Perfection, will adequately fulfill his duty to his homeland. And the first stage of spiritual perfection begins with a focus on Physical Culture and sports at a higher level. Our First President I. Karimov In the following words of, this can be understood even more deeply: "through sports, the child's worldview changes. A child who walked the street yesterday, not knowing what to do, will also look at his parents with a different eye if he is busy with work and sports activities by learning a craft. In the family, Kindness, Harmony increases. Boys in particular pass a school of bravery on sports grounds." It is known to everyone today that in order to educate and educate the perfect generation, first of all, it is necessary to form in them a love of sports, and in the pursuit of these noble goals, our president creates all opportunities.

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